

WP3 – Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services

Proof-of-Concept towards a Biodiversity Tool for Agroforestry Systems

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Summary

Agroforestry can enhance biodiversity conservation in agroecosystems, but it is still difficult to quantify such outputs. This study combines insights from meta-analyses, a stakeholder questionnaire, and an inventory of biodiversity assessment tools to develop a way to quantify biodiversity outcomes.

Through meta-analyses, we evaluated the impact of agroforestry on biodiversity across various functional groups within agroecosystems. Results indicate predominantly positive or neutral effects, highlighting the potential of agroforestry practices in fostering biodiversity, albeit with contextual nuances. Complementing this literature evidence, we carried out a stakeholder questionnaire discerning the perceptions and preferences of stakeholders. The results underscored stakeholders' recognition of biodiversity's pivotal role in agroecosystems, revealing a willingness to invest time and effort in assessing biodiversity within agroforestry settings. Stakeholders indicated that tool outputs and functionalities should be user-friendly and they indicated a preference for web-based tools integrating mapping features and checklists which could be used for diverse agroforestry types. An evaluation of 55 biodiversity tools and their capability of incorporating agroforestry components revealed limitations in terms of specificity, accessibility, and capacity to encompass the wide range of agroforestry configurations.

This interdisciplinary synthesis underscores the potential of agroforestry in promoting biodiversity while emphasizing the need for a nuanced, user-centric tool to effectively assess biodiversity within agroecosystems. Such a tool might be constructed with input-data for different agroforestry types, across several species groups and deterministic evaluation for situations where data availability is limited. The required comprehensibility could be achieved by using checklists for farm characteristics and mapping features as inputs through a website-based or computer program interface.

1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 to June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Participatory research approach is key to engage with actors involved in the development of agroforestry and to unlock synergies among stakeholders and other research to facilitate the implementation of innovations. An overall objective of the project is to provide three groups of stakeholders with digital tools that address their needs and expectation. The three groups of stakeholders addressed by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

This report introduces and presents the work conducted to establish the needs and wishes of stakeholders for a biodiversity tool concerning agroforestry and to review existing biodiversity tools and databases along with scientific meta-analyses upon biodiversity effects in such landscapes.

This deliverable (D3.3) forms part of work-package 3 in the DigitAF project which deals with the verification and accounting of the benefits of agroforestry practices for stakeholders in the value chain. An anticipated output of the work-package is an enhanced capacity of actors to identify and account for the economic, environmental and social performances of agroforestry.

D3.3 arises from Task 3.3 which has the objective of co-developing, applying and verifying a tool to quantify the biodiversity impact of agroforestry, which will be validated through field work in different European regions. This report describes the approach towards developing a proof-of-concept for a biodiversity tool, through the evaluation of existing tools, investigating the needs and wishes of stakeholders, and reviewing scientific evidence in the form of meta-analyses.

2 Introduction

2.1 Biodiversity in agricultural landscapes

Healthy, biodiverse environments are vital for a well-functioning planet, as biodiversity is an important driver of the optimal delivery of ecosystem services such as pest control, pollination and nutrient cycling (Dainese et al., 2019; Lindemann-Matthies et al., 2010; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Despite its importance, biodiversity is under threat (Butchart et al., 2010; Sachs et al., 2009). This unprecedented and accelerated loss of biodiversity (Sodhi & Ehrlich, 2010) is combined with an altered interaction among species (Tylianakis et al., 2008) and a decline in associated ecosystem functioning (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The loss of biodiversity has been acknowledged by policy makers (European Commission, 2011) who have implemented measures to preserve and restore biodiversity. In Europe this is now embodied by, among others, the Green Deal and the Biodiversity Strategy to 2030 (European Commission & Directorate-General for Environment, 2021).

During recent decades, expansion and intensification of agriculture have been important drivers of biodiversity loss, mainly through the disappearance of natural and semi-natural land and small landscape elements (Balmford et al., 2012; Burel et al., 2004; Gonthier et al., 2014; Rudel et al., 2009; Tilman et al., 2001; Tschardt et al., 2012). In many European areas, agricultural land includes a matrix of connected remnant and fragmented patches of natural vegetation, often described as semi-natural habitats, where non-domesticated biodiversity persists (Goulson, 2021). Increasing the habitat options within this matrix is one critical method to halt biodiversity loss (Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022; Perfecto & Vandermeer, 2008, 2010). As agricultural land takes up about 40% of the EU's land area (European Commission & Eurostat, 2022), increasing biodiversity in those systems could have large impacts.

2.2 Potential biodiversity benefit of agroforestry

One way of increasing biodiversity in monoculture arable or grassland fields is to introduce trees and shrubs (Leakey, 1996), and the possible production of nuts, fruit or wood from the trees can offset possible yield losses in the monoculture crop. Such practices have been termed agroforestry. Examples of agroforestry include silvoarable systems (tree-crop associations) and silvopastoral activities (tree-livestock associations), hedgerows, forest grazing-practices and scattered solitary trees (Mosquera-Losada et al., 2009). Each of these agroforestry types are considered in the later stages of this report. Agroforestry can lead to enhanced provision of ecosystem services (Udawatta et al., 2019) by providing food, shelter, habitat and the provision of more diverse resources to multiple species (Jose, 2009; McAdam et al., 2009). Some authors have argued that the assessment of the effects of agroforestry on biodiversity in temperate regions has been less studied than in tropical regions (Staton et al., 2019). However, several studies indicate positive effects of agroforestry on biodiversity in comparison to monoculture (Pardon et al., 2019; Plieninger et al., 2015; Varah et al., 2020), whilst others state the opposite (Imbert et al., 2020). The net effect of agroforestry on biodiversity is thus likely to depend on its implementation, the context of the system and the species of focus.

2.3 The role of a surrounding landscape

The potential biodiversity benefit of agroforestry may depend on the landscape as context-wise variability. The complexity of the landscape structure influences species occurrence by providing habitats that can maintain source populations (Öckinger & Smith, 2007). For example, structurally

complex landscapes can offer a variety of habitats by forming either a complex matrix, lots of semi-natural habitats or a combination of both (Concepción et al., 2008; Tschardt et al., 2005). By contrast, structurally simple landscapes typically offer a limited number of habitats and are characterized by a rather uniform agricultural matrix containing few semi-natural habitats (Tschardt et al., 2005). Cleared landscapes form an even poorer landscape containing (almost) no semi-natural habitats. In the literature, the term landscape complexity comprises both the composition (e.g., the amount of semi-natural habitats) of a landscape and its configuration (e.g., field size, connectivity of habitats) (Fahrig et al., 2011; Hass et al., 2018).

Landscape structure has also been found to mediate the effect of mitigation measures like agri-environmental schemes and increasing the coverage of semi-natural habitats (Scheper et al., 2013; Sirami et al., 2019). Therefore, it may be expected that the effect of agroforestry will also depend on the current landscape context. Integrating agroforestry in landscapes with a mix of forests and agriculture might achieve the highest biodiversity added value (Rolo et al., 2021). For bats, for instance, it is clear that the connectivity of woody features is more important than its structure (Park, 2015). Agroforestry thus might play a role in connecting semi-natural habitats through an agricultural matrix. However, other hypotheses claim that positive effects of agroforestry might be larger in simple landscapes in comparison to its effectiveness in complex landscapes (Sánchez et al., 2022). Recent reviews and meta-analyses on temperate agroforestry concluded that further research is needed to determine the interactive effect of landscape and agroforestry on biodiversity and ecosystem services.

2.4 Biodiversity assessment tools

With the aforementioned biodiversity crisis in mind, it is important to properly account for the possible biodiversity gains that could be attained through agro-ecological measures like agroforestry. However, biodiversity is a highly complex term, which makes it difficult to score. As a result, even farmers attentive to biodiversity are often uncertain about their options to enhance biodiversity (Birrer et al., 2014). These observations were also observed by Dwyer et al. (2023) from a pollinator perspective. Hence, it would be helpful to develop methods to assess biodiversity in efficient and easy-to-interpret ways. This will (1) enable farmers to assess and understand the biodiversity on their farms and (2) provide a clear interpretable metric that can be used to report downstream. In turn it is likely that describing this biodiversity proxies to other stakeholders requires evidence-based, practical tools.

2.5 Knowledge gap and set-up

At present, there is no policy- or management-supporting tool available to assess the biodiversity benefits of agroforestry. Such a tool might enable the appropriate labelling of agroforestry products, which is important to both farmers and value chain actors.

With this study, we aimed to identify the key building blocks of an evidence-based tool that can predict the biodiversity benefits of agroforestry implementation in agroecosystems. Therefore, we compiled scientific evidence, based on published meta-analyses, about agroforestry systems and their effect on biodiversity in agroecosystems. To account for landscape effects, we included meta-analyses on landscape complexity in agroecosystems. Additionally, a questionnaire was distributed to stakeholders within the DigitAF consortium to qualitatively and quantitatively discern their requirements and preferences concerning a biodiversity tool in agroforestry. Lastly, we compiled available biodiversity tools, that are used around the globe to predict biodiversity in a simplified way.

We then evaluated these tools upon the criteria we established with the meta-analyses and questionnaire. The intention was that this multifaceted approach would allow us to gain comprehensive insights on the building blocks needed for an evidence-based and user-friendly tool that allows the prediction of the effect of agroforestry on biodiversity in agroecosystems.

3 Meta-analysis review

3.1 Method

Existing meta-analyses can provide a summary of the best scientific evidence for a specific topic as they provide a quantitative summary of existing research. In the meta-analyses, the impacts in case-studies have already been converted to comparable effect-sizes, which can be contrasted and used to summarize the effects across a large range of contexts.

We performed a systematic literature search to identify suitable meta-analyses for our objectives. Our search was performed in February 2023, using ("biodiversity" OR "agrodiversity" OR "diversity") AND ("meta-analysis" OR "meta analysis") in ISI Web of Science Core Collection, resulting in 3911 articles. Included studies had to meet the following criteria: (1) the study was a meta-analysis, (2) at least partially making use of studies performed in temperate climates, (3) the meta-analysis studied biodiversity effects in terrestrial ecosystems and (4) the meta-analysis used one or more biodiversity metrics as response variables. Studies solely built on genetic diversity were excluded. Additionally, we scanned the first 100 results in Scopus (sorted by relevance) that were considered after removing all articles not belonging to relevant research domains using: AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "AGRI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "EART")), using the same term as above, resulting in one additional meta-analysis. In Google Scholar, using the same term as above, the first 100 records were reviewed when sorted by relevance, but no additional records were added. We noticed that no meta-analysis concerning hedgerows was retrieved, therefore, an additional term ("Meta-analysis" AND "biodiversity" AND "hedgerows") was inserted in Google Scholar and the first page (10 records) was revised, adding one meta-analysis to the database, using the same selection criteria as described above.

This approach resulted in 80 meta-analyses. We summarized all biodiversity-related effect sizes within those studies assessing each individual effect size to extract its theme, species group, reference unit and metric being used. More information is available in Annex III. This process resulted in 1659 relevant study-level effect sizes. Given our focus on agroforestry in agro-environments and landscape contexts, we extracted only the effect sizes relating to these topics. Annex III gives a detailed overview on the methods used. This process resulted in a final set of 10 meta-analyses (Annex III) and 159 corresponding effect sizes (25 effect sizes are relevant in two categories, leading to 184 responses). We produced a PRISMA-diagram, available in Annex III. We visualized these effect sizes by using a votecount per meta-analysis, per functional group and per significance level (positive, neutral, negative).

Data were analyzed with R (R Core Team, 2023), with packages dplyr (Wickham, François, et al., 2023), tidyr (Wickham, Vaughan, et al., 2023), forcats (Wickham, 2023), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), gridExtra (Auguie, 2017) and ggpattern (FC et al., 2022).

3.2 Results and discussion

Five meta-analyses (García de León et al., 2021; Mupepele et al., 2021; Prevedello et al., 2018; Staton et al., 2019; Torralba et al., 2016) were used to assess the effects of agroforestry on biodiversity in agroecosystems, accounting for 73 effect sizes, as visualized in Figure 1. Only a limited number of agroforestry-like features were assessed through meta-analyses for different functional groups. We retrieved studies wherein agroforestry in general, silvoarable, silvopasture, hedgerows and scattered trees are represented.

Figure 1: A votecount diagram showing the number of effect sizes that are either significantly positive, negative or non-significant for each meta-analysis concerning agroforestry, respectively plotted in the green, red or white area, divided by functional groups of biodiversity. The underlying effect sizes are based on abundance, diversity and richness metrics and are compared to their baselines (agroecosystems without agroforestry). 'Agroforestry' shows effect sizes accounting for overall agroforestry and includes its subgroups silvoarable and silvopasture. The colors of the dots and silhouettes appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species. The number of effect sizes indicates the amount of effect sizes we extracted for each study and level of significance. (d = (García de León et al., 2021), f = (Mupepele et al., 2021), g = (Prevedello et al., 2018), i = (Staton et al., 2019), j = (Torralba et al., 2016)). Species groups silhouettes were retrieved from phylopic.org.

Only 5 out of 73 effect sizes report negative results on biodiversity, including two within the functional group of pest species. Thus, these observations are positive towards agricultural practices. The broader share of effect sizes reports neutral or positive effects. The meta-analyses thus acknowledge the value agroforestry might contribute to boost biodiversity. This is in line with results in other geographical areas (De Beenhouwer et al., 2013; Schroth et al., 2004), confirming the premise that

structurally and functionally more complex land-use systems result in greater biodiversity. However, the variation within the results is high, indicating that the magnitude of the effects is context related. Influences caused by differences in agroforestry design, management or configuration are expected (Jose, 2009; Kletty et al., 2023). Variation may also arise due to the benefits provided depend on the context of the land use selected for the comparison (Boinot et al., 2022). Kletty et al. (2023) reported in their review unsystematic effects of silvoarable agroforestry on biodiversity, identifying studies that approached different aspects that might affect biodiversity effects. They defined affecting factors as applied taxa, diversity metrics, management, age, site location, environment, climate, landscape context, comparison type and sampling.

Another five meta-analyses (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2011; Coutinho et al., 2018; Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022; Marja et al., 2022; Shackelford et al., 2013) assess the mitigation effects on biodiversity in agroecosystems due to landscape complexity, accounting for 111 effect sizes, as visualized in Figure 2. Overall, no negative correlations of increasing landscape complexity were reported and there is a more uniform consensus for positive impacts across all functional groups assessed. This evidence supports the knowledge that a landscape context influences local biodiversity, with a positive response in more complex landscapes.

Figure 2: A votecount diagram showing the number of effect sizes that are either significantly positive, negative or non-significant for each meta-analysis concerning landscape complexity, respectively plotted in the green, red or white area, divided by functional groups of biodiversity. The underlying effect sizes are based on abundance, diversity and richness metrics and are compared to their baselines (agroecosystems without the woody feature). The colors of the dots and silhouettes appoint a species group's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species. The number of effect sizes indicates the amount of effect sizes we extracted for each study and level of significance. (a = (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2011), b = (Coutinho et al., 2018), c = (Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022), e = (Marja et al., 2022), h = (Shackelford et al., 2013)). Species groups silhouettes were retrieved from phylopic.org.

Yet, four meta-analyses in our review, accounting for 108 effect sizes (Annex III), tackle interactions between agro-ecological measures and this landscape context, all agreeing that landscape does mitigate biodiversity responses (Batáry et al., 2011; Lichtenberg et al., 2017; Sánchez et al., 2022;

Scheper et al., 2013). These interaction effects merely influence the magnitude of the effects, rather than the level of significance, rendering it impractical to visualize these effects as vote counting. Few studies accounted for this interaction in an agroforestry context (Kletty et al., 2023) with no data on meta-analysis-level available, a knowledge gap future research could investigate.

Further gaps occur concerning different agroforestry types and in distinguishing different functional groups on meta-analysis level. No pollinator analysis was available (however there are certain studies addressing the topic e.g., Varah et al., 2020) and a lack of data on several other functional groups occurred. We could only retrieve meta-analyses for agroforestry in general, silvoarable, silvopasture, hedgerows, scattered trees and forest grazing (Li & Jiang, 2021). Other practices (i.e., food forest-approaches) are not covered. Most meta-analyses combine comparisons between agroforestry and agroecosystem- and natural baselines, making conclusions about agroforestry's effect on biodiversity towards agroecosystems impractical. The likely approach would be to compare an agroforestry treatment with the proper baseline without agroforestry being applied.

4 Questionnaire

4.1 Method

We undertook a large survey in which we disentangled the stakeholder's needs and wishes for a biodiversity tool, specifically designed to aid biodiversity estimation in agroforestry systems. We targeted specifically three actors' groups: (1) policy makers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry, (2) farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers (who were categorized separately) playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond and (3) stakeholders in the value chain including wholesalers, retailers, organizations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms. The questionnaire was distributed in several stakeholder groups, established as Living Labs functioning within the DigitAF project (<https://digitaf.eu/>). These were situated in Finland, the Czech Republic, the Netherlands, Germany (Brandenburg), United Kingdom (Cambridgeshire and Northamptonshire) and Italy (Tuscany). Another stakeholder group was used with the consortium of 'Agroforestry Vlaanderen' in Belgium (Flanders). Further information can be obtained through Deliverable 2.1 in the project (Tranchina et al., 2023).

Different segments within the questionnaire were customized, encompassing questions upon (1) the importance of biodiversity and its assessment, (2) the required specifications and relevance of an agroforestry-based biodiversity tool, (3) the design of such a tool and (4) interests concerning its validation (Annex I). We chose to display the results in a qualitative way.

In total, 82 respondents across the different regions completed the questionnaire. Czech Republic accounted for most respondents (28), Finland for the least (6). Farmers and land owners represented 45.6% of the respondents, researchers 16.3%, farm advisers 13.0% and policy actors 10.9% of the respondents. Stakeholders in the value chain and others accounted for 13.0% of the respondents (acknowledging that one respondent could be assigned to two stakeholder groups). Further respondent characteristics can be retrieved in Annex II.

Data were analyzed with R (R Core Team, 2023), with packages dplyr (Wickham, François, et al., 2023), tidyr (Wickham, Vaughan, et al., 2023), forcats (Wickham, 2023), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), gridExtra (Auguie, 2017) and ggpattern (FC et al., 2022).

4.2 Results and discussion

Most of the respondents recognise the importance of biodiversity in agroecosystems (Figure 3, A and B), with 79.3% valuing biodiversity as very important and an additionally 13.4% valuing biodiversity as important. García de Jalón et al. (2018) previously observed this pattern, also consistent with the work performed by Herzog et al. (2012). About 60% of the stakeholders indicated that a biodiversity assessment tool concerning agroforestry was important (very important = 34.2% and important = 26.8%). Most of the respondents did not have experience with existing biodiversity tools: only 9 respondents (11.0%) claimed to use or to be familiar with existing tools.

Concerning the functioning of a tool, most stakeholders express preferences towards tools accessible through websites and specifically designed computer programs. Most stakeholders prefer a tool on farm scale, but differences were small. Stakeholders did express the utility of integrating both mapping features (79.3%) and checklists for farm characteristics (89.0%) as inputs. The first could imply habitat (quality) maps and landscape maps to reduce work to complete the tool, the latter could then imply specific habitat features and managements, mainly tailored towards agroforestry.

All proposed outputs for a biodiversity tool were considered useful by 55% of the stakeholders. Preferences are (1) calculating the effects established by different agroforestry types and (2) proposing actions to increase biodiversity, with about 70% of the stakeholders opting for these choices (Figure 3, F). Enabling the estimation of proxies for biodiversity within different species groups or for total biodiversity are somewhat less favoured.

Figure 3: Graph bars illustrating the relevance of biodiversity and a tool assessing biodiversity according to the stakeholders, expressed in percentage of stakeholders. (A): Importance of agrobiodiversity according to the stakeholders. (B): Perceived urgency to create a new tool, specifically designed to assess biodiversity in agroforestry systems, according to the stakeholders. (C): Desired interface the stakeholders want for a biodiversity tool. (D): Scale for which the stakeholders want a biodiversity tool to work with. (E): Practices that might be incorporated in a biodiversity tool (addressed to farmers and advisors only). (FarmChar: checklist for management practices and habitats on/close by the farm or field, Woody: the amount/characterization of woody species at the farm/field, BioChar: checklist for presence or absence of several charismatic and easy-to-record key species). (F): Needs of stakeholders in relation to a helpful output of a biodiversity tool (EffAF = effects of different agroforestry types, PropAct = proposed actions towards improving biodiversity, MetricSpGr = species groups biodiversity, MetricBio = total biodiversity).

A separate part of the questionnaire was directed towards farmers and advisors, the likely assessors of farm scaled biodiversity, where we tried to disentangle the effort they were willing to invest to assess biodiversity. The stakeholders exhibited a preparedness to allocate some time for the

assessment of biodiversity. More explicitly, there was a larger interest in using a checklist for on-farm habitats, structures and management practices in combination with specifications of the agroforestry elements. However, assessing basic biodiversity metrics (e.g., with a checklist of charismatic species to encounter on a farm) was never completely rejected and answered positively by more than half of the respondents (Figure 3, E). Spontaneous extra options revealed certain suggestions to enable farmers to assess farmland biodiversity by using either a checklist of several species or enabling photograph identification. Furthermore, detailed suggestions indicated a further interest towards the design of agroforestry to benefit biodiversity.

5 Biodiversity tools review

5.1 Method

We performed a broad-spectrum search of biodiversity tools between November 2022 and September 2023 to build a comprehensive database of tools used to assess biodiversity in terrestrial ecosystems. Some of these tools are able to assess biodiversity in agroforestry systems. A detailed description of the selection process is available through Annex IV. Our refinement of the tools database resulted in 18 tools. For these tools, we categorized the input-output relations in different categories (Table 1), distinguishing between the input variables that tools are using and which outputs they present with that information. As such, there are tools using habitat characterization (structure quality), biotic indicators (sampling of species group) or both as inputs. Additionally, we highlighted the typology concerning woody structures incorporated in the tools, referring to its applicability in specific agroforestry types (Table 1). Furthermore, the tools were evaluated upon their open source-availability.

Table 1: Three categorizations of biodiversity tools: Applicability: the woody structures a tool is using in its process. Input: the different input types a tool is using. Output: the different output types a tool gives.

Applicability	Input	Output
Tree: <i>The feasibility of implementing scattered or solitary trees.</i>	Woody: <i>The input requires at least a basic distinction of woody features. This can emerge as different types or as in-type specification (structure, species).</i>	Metric of biodiversity (MetricBio): <i>The output consists of a proxy for total biodiversity (at least defined by a proper corresponding landscape value such as habitat diversity).</i>
Hedge: <i>The feasibility of implementing hedges/hedgerows.</i>	Farm characteristics (FarmChar): <i>The input requires farm characteristics, those can include farmland habitats, farm features, farm management, ...</i>	Metric of a species group (MetricSpGr): <i>The output consists of a proxy for at least 1 specific biodiversity group (at least defined by a proper corresponding variable such as predation or pollination).</i>
Agroforestry (AF): <i>The feasibility of implementing agroforestry in general (this category contains the agglomerate of SP, SA and FF).</i>	Maps: <i>The input requires maps of the study site itself, which can be used to define in-situ habitat composition and/or complexity, biotic occurrences, ...</i>	Effect of agroforestry (EffAF): <i>The output consists of biodiversity differences provoked by different woody feature implementation or at least offers the option to do so.</i>
Silvopasture (SP): <i>The feasibility of implementing silvopastoral systems. These can be applied as well through a pasture layer and sole trees or tree rows within.</i>	Biodiversity characterization (BioChar): <i>The input requires abundance or presence-absence data for at least one species group.</i>	Proposed actions (PropAct): <i>The output consists of actions that can be implemented to boost biodiversity levels or at least offers the option to identify these.</i>
Silvoarable (SA): <i>The feasibility of implementing silvoarable systems. These can be applied as well through arable layers and sole trees or tree rows within.</i>	Landscape complexity (LndscpCompl): <i>The input requires maps of the surrounding landscape for the study site to enable ex-situ landscape complexity calculation.</i>	
Food forest (FF): <i>The feasibility of implementing food forests or alike systems (berry gardens).</i>		
Forest Grazing (FG): <i>The feasibility of implementing of grazed forests.</i>		

We established a point of view (POV) of the stakeholders to compare the tools efficiently, which we assessed by means of the questionnaire outputs, assigning to each category the percentage of stakeholders valuing that particular category. For those that were not asked during the questionnaire, we assigned the median value 0.5. For this dataset we performed both Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) using function `metaMDS` with Bray-Curtis distance and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using function `prcomp`.

Data were analyzed with R (R Core Team, 2023), with packages `dplyr` (Wickham, François, et al., 2023), `tidyr` (Wickham, Vaughan, et al., 2023), `forcats` (Wickham, 2023), `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016), `ggrepel` (Slowikowski, 2023), `gridExtra` (Auguie, 2017), `ggpattern` (FC et al., 2022), `factoextra` (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020), `vegan` (Oksanen et al., 2022) and `goeveg` (von Lampe & Schellenberg, 2023).

5.2 Results and discussion

Present biodiversity assessment tools exhibit a lack of specificity in their capacity to evaluate diverse agroforestry strategies. Stewart et al. (2022) concluded in their agroforestry-specific review that there were few tools able to score biodiversity which often only scored particular species or habitat types. Yet, still 18 tools in our database incorporate considerations for agroforestry, of which only 6 demonstrate the capability to accommodate two distinct agroforestry types, enabling a nuanced differentiation between them. Particularly noteworthy are the Biodiversity Metric and Ecological Focus Area calculator (EFA), recognized for their capacity to address a greater number of agroforestry types, respectively 6 and 5 (of seven types defined in Table 1). We compiled the 18 tools that were considered usable in agroecosystems and integrating at least one form of woody characterization, meaning they could be applied in agroforestry systems (Table 2).

The tools present different approaches: some tools are merely based on mapping features and award biodiversity scores to habitat types, whilst others were based on checklists for farm practices and features with many variations between both. Four tools will be discussed shortly to identify some of the key approaches and the pitfalls along.

The Biodiversity Metric differentiates over 100 habitats and requires a detailed mapping of the area that will be assessed (Panks et al., 2022). This complex habitat distinction impedes accessibility for non-experts. The Credit Point System (CPS) implements an entirely different approach. It makes use of an exhaustive and user-friendly questionnaire format (Birrer et al., 2014). However, this approach falls short in providing quantitative values for separate species groups, and its narrow agroforestry-related implementation options limits its applicability from an agroforestry perspective.

Table 2: Tools enabling biodiversity assessment in agroecosystems with agroforestry. Type: type of interface (WT = webtool, S = spreadsheet, GIS = geographic information system-tool, R = programming tool, TG = guidelines, CP = computer program). Scale: scale the tool is applicable to; please note that farm scale tools are highly flexible and as such applicable at the plot or regional scale (F = farm scale, L = landscape/regional scale, P = plot/field scale). Applicability: the agroforestry element that a tool is using in its process (Hedge = hedgerows, AF = agroforestry, SP = Silvopasture, SA = silvoarable, FF = food forest, FG = forest grazing). Input: the different input types that a tool is using (Woody = implementation of agroforestry basic characterization, FarmChar = checklist of farm characteristics, Maps = habitat/environment mapping, BioChar = checklist for biotic indicators, LndscpCompl = landscape complexity). Output: the different output types a tool gives (MetricBio = one global metric for overall biodiversity, MetricSpGr = one or more metrics for specific species groups, EffAF = effects of different agroforestry types, PropAct = proposed actions towards improving biodiversity). When characterizations were not fully integrated, but for which a proxy is taken into account (Annex IV), these are displayed in grey. POV = point of view.

Tool	Type	Scale	Applicability	Input	Output
CPS	WT, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge	Woody, FarmChar	MetricBio
Biodiversity metric	S, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge, AF, SP, SA, FF	Woody, Maps	MetricBio, EffAF
Nature Smart Cities¹	S, TG	P, F, L	Tree	Woody, Maps	MetricBio,
Nature Smart Cities²	S, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge, FF	Woody, FarmChar	MetricSpGr, PropAct
ASSET	WT	L	AF	FarmChar, Maps	MetricBio, MetricSpGr
BEST	S	P, F, L	Hedge	Maps	MetricBio
EcoServ	GIS, R, TG	L	Hedge	Maps	MetricBio, MetricSpGr
Biodiversity Footprint Calculator	WT, TG	P, F, L	AF	FarmChar, Maps	MetricBio
NOP Biodiversity Guidance	WT, TG	P, F, L	AF	Woody, FarmChar	MetricBio, MetricSpGr
EFA	CP, TG	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge, AF, SP, SA	Woody, FarmChar	MetricBio, MetricSpGr, EffAF
SPIES	WT, TG	P, F, L	Hedge	Woody, FarmChar	PropAct
SENCE	GIS, TG	P, F, L	Hedge	FarmChar, Maps	MetricBio, MetricSpGr
Habitat Hectares	TG	P, F, L	Tree, AF, SP	Woody, Maps	MetricBio
CFT	WT	P, F, L	Tree, Hedge	LndscpCompl, Woody, FarmChar	MetricSpGr
B-INTACT	CP, TG	P, F, L	AF	FarmChar, Maps	MetricBio
GLOBIO	CP, TG	P, F, L	AF	Maps	metricBio, MetricSpGr
Agri-environment Biodiversity Index	TG	P, F, L	Hedge	FarmChar	MetricBio
Index of agrobiodiversity	TG	P, F, L	Tree	FarmChar	MetricBio
LOOC-B	WT, TG	P, F, L	AF	Maps, BioChar	MetricBio

It is pertinent to highlight that both tools yield deterministic, knowledge-based outputs. Conversely, GLOBIO adopts a data-driven output for predicting different habitat types based on its access to a global biodiversity empiric database, offering a quantitative estimation for habitat assessment. Its global approach however imposes limitations on the number of assessable habitats, rendering it incapable of accommodating various agroforestry types and lacking distinctions among ecosystem regions (Alkemade et al., 2009). Another approach to avoid the use of deterministic inputs or the need for yet established empiric databases is the use of actual, in-situ, biodiversity data (Freyman et al., 2016), but the data gathering for such tools might require expert-knowledge. Using data from open source biodiversity databases (Callaghan et al., 2020) might solve this. Since the beginning of this century, biodiversity databases, often open source, are rapidly being created and expanded (Hobern et al., 2019) with the aid of citizen science (Pocock et al., 2017). However, observer effects and presence of active observers highly influence the quality of this data.

In our non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) analysis of biodiversity tools (stress = 0.181, corresponding scree plot in Annex IV), we observed distinct patterns of tool relationships (Figure 4). Noteworthy are BEST, ASSET and Nature Smart Cities (2) as the least similar tools, suggesting significant differences in their approaches. This distinction in tool relationships is primarily influenced by the variables forest grazing (FG), applicability, the programming tool (R) and silvoarable (SA), which play pivotal roles in driving the observed distinctions. The presence or absence of these variables significantly impacts the positioning of tools along the first axes of our analysis (Annex IV). Separately, a point of view (POV) for stakeholders in the analysis. The Biodiversity Metric, EFA and Habitat Hectares coincided most with the stakeholders' POV, while EcoServ, BEST and ASSET coincided the least. An additional Principal Component Analysis (Annex IV) largely supported these findings, however using other primary variables. This shows the robustness of the distinction.

Figure 4: Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling for biodiversity tool frameworks. StakePOV represents the needs of stakeholders based on the questionnaire.

6 Conclusions

In the questionnaire, stakeholders emphasized the significance of being able to assess the distinctions between the effects of different agroforestry implementations and express a pronounced interest in actions promoting biodiversity. Their preference lies in outputs focusing on multiple species groups rather than singular ones. Additionally, stakeholders articulated a desire for tools that integrate mapping data and factors describing the farm, mainly focused on woody characterizations to define agroforestry. Unfortunately, a tool encapsulating all these facets is presently unavailable. The tools most closely aligned with these preferences (e.g., the Biodiversity Metric, EFA and Habitat Hectares) present challenges in terms of complexity and, moreover, are not specifically tailored to agroforestry. Therefore, there is need for either a new, or an adapted biodiversity assessment tool, tailored to agroforestry, that is both science-based, but still sufficiently simple.

Stakeholders expressed the need for a tool to account for different agroforestry types, preferably for different species groups, that can show the options they can take to improve biodiversity. The likely set-up for such a tool should start from a baseline upon which agroforestry is implemented. This requires well-suited input-data for this baseline alongside the effect of different agroforestry types compared with this baseline, across several species groups. Such detailed scientific information is however not yet available in the format of meta-analyses as there is still a lack of data for certain functional groups (Figure 1), the variability in baselines and/or there is a difference in scope (Boinot et al., 2022; Mupepele & Dormann, 2022). As this is an area of fast-progressing research, there will be benefits from performing new meta-analyses to establish a database better suited towards effects of different functional groups for different agroforestry types.

Our analysis suggests that stakeholders are willing to spend time to assess biodiversity, preferring comprehensive tools, adapted to its intended end-users, preferably available through websites or computer programs. They also expressed the utility of integrating both checklists for farm characteristics and mapping features. Farm characteristics could encompass specific habitat features and management strategies, mainly tailored towards agroforestry. Some characteristics (e.g. agroforestry type, age, species) might be assessed empirically. However, current empirical evidence would not meet the requirements to account for specific agroforestry designs and management strategies due to the wide range of agroforestry types and the relative low number of studies (Kletty et al., 2023). One way to include these factors is to use deterministic evidence. Mapping features-inclusion could enable remote habitat (quality) assessment. Furthermore, this option enables landscape complexity inclusion to account for mitigating effects between agro-ecological measures and landscape contexts as literature evidence suggests.

Currently, certain efforts are made to improve existing biodiversity tools for agroecosystems in European context. FEAST, a tool currently being constructed, includes the framework of its predecessor EFA (Douglas & Tzilivakis, 2022) and will additionally include a mapping interface and biodiversity monitoring data, using citizen science within established [farming clusters](#) (Banks et al., 2023; Hager et al., 2022, 2023). Simultaneously, TAPE, a tool that as of yet does not integrate woody features (FAO, 2019), aims at introducing the BioBio-indicators. These indicators were evaluated as proper indicators to reflect farmland biodiversity (Herzog et al., 2012). Whilst both approaches appear valuable, their complexity for the user still needs to be evaluated, and neither of these tools will specifically target agroforestry. There is still a gap for a tool that explicitly meets the need and wishes

of agroforestry stakeholders, enabling a straight-forward application and making it easy-to-retrieve with proper communication. Although we reviewed 55 tools that enable biodiversity assessment, only a handful of our questionnaire respondents indicated that they knew or used such tools and a far higher share expressed the importance of biodiversity tools for agroforestry.

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Annex I – Relevant parts of the DigitAF survey

*: Multiple answers possible

Overall characteristics of a survey respondents

- 1) I confirm that I have read and understand the information provided on this form and give my consent to taking part in this research.
 - a. Accept/Decline
- 2) Please indicate if this response is part of the testing process or if it's the actual response you wish to give to the questions.
 - a. "Test" answer/Actual answer
- 3) Please enter your personal code below. This was previously assigned to you by DigitAF staff.
- 4) Please select your age?
 - a. 18-35 years old
 - b. 36-50 years old
 - c. 51-65 years old
 - d. 66+ years old
 - e. Prefer not to say
- 5) What is your gender?
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Other
 - d. Prefer not to say
- 6) In which countries do you carry out your business or activities?
- 7) What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 - a. No formal education
 - b. Secondary school (up to 16y old)
 - c. High school (up to 18y old)
 - d. Bachelor's degree or equivalent
 - e. Master's degree or equivalent
 - f. Doctoral or above
- 8) What type of stakeholder are you?
 - a. Farmer and/or landowner
 - b. Farm advisor
 - c. Policymaker
 - d. Stakeholder in the value chain
 - e. Researcher
 - f. ...
- 9) Please indicate the size of your farm in ha?
- 10) What is your farm type? *
 - a. Arable
 - b. Horticulture (vegetables)
 - c. Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine)
 - d. Mixed (Livestock + Crops)
 - e. Livestock (Pigs)
 - f. Livestock (Poultry)
 - g. Livestock (Beef and sheep)
 - h. Livestock (Dairy)
 - i. Agroforestry
 - j. Forestry
 - k. Agri-tourism and education
 - l. Organic
 - m. ...
- 11) What types of farm do you advise? *
 - a. Arable
 - b. Horticulture (vegetables)
 - c. Horticulture tree crops (e.g. Olive, apples, vine)
 - d. Mixed (Livestock + Crops)
 - e. Livestock (Pigs)
 - f. Livestock (Poultry)
 - g. Livestock (Beef and sheep)
 - h. Livestock (Dairy)
 - i. Agroforestry
 - j. Forestry
 - k. Agri-tourism and education
 - l. Organic
 - m. ...
- 12) Do you also have a secondary stakeholder role?
ex. you're a farmer but you're also a researcher
 - a. Yes, Farmer and/or landowner
 - b. Yes, Farm advisor
 - c. Yes, Policymaker
 - d. Yes, Stakeholder in the value chain
 - e. Yes, Researcher
 - f. No, I do not have a secondary stakeholder role

Biodiversity

PA: Questions included for policy actors (all the questions are asked to farmers and advisors)

The importance of biodiversity and its assessment

The primary target of agriculture is the production of consumable food, however, agricultural practices can lend additional benefits as habitat for numerous of species and benefit biodiversity as such.

Alas, the past decades, a severe decline in agriculture-related biodiversity was observed. Hence there is a lot of research going on to assess biodiversity properly in agricultural systems.

With biodiversity we here mean all species groups (plants, birds, insects, mammals, ...) that occur in or around agricultural fields and that are likely to be affected by agroforestry practices. We perform this survey to investigate the desires and interests of the stakeholders that can make use of our research.

- 1) How important do you consider biodiversity in agroecosystems? **PA**
 - a. Likert scale (Not at all important/Somewhat important/Neutral/important/Very important)
- 2) Do you know any biodiversity assessment models or tools (software to quantify biodiversity)? **PA**
 - a. Yes/No
- 3) If yes, which ones? **PA**
- 4) Do you think a model or tool predicting biodiversity in AF systems would be useful? **PA**

This tool could be used to enter the specifications of a field/farm and would give as an output a proxy for biodiversity under these circumstances.

 - a. Likert scale (Not at all important/Somewhat important/Neutral/important/Very important)
 - i. → exclude users that answer 'not important'
- 5) Briefly explain why? **PA**

Specifics and relevance of an agroforestry-based biodiversity tool

- 6) Which output would you expect from a biodiversity model or tool? * **PA**
 - a. An overall score for total biodiversity on the farm/field
 - b. A score for several specific species groups (e.g. birds, mammals, insects, plants, ...)
 - c. A proxy for biodiversity effects generated by implementing agroforestry elements
 - d. Proposed actions (e.g. hedgerow planting) to increase biodiversity on the farm/field
 - e. ...
- 7) If you chose 'A score for several specific species groups (e.g. birds, mammals, insects, plants, soil fauna, pollinators, ...) biodiversity' in the previous question: which species groups would have preference and why? * **PA**

(Add as many as you desire on separate lines.)
- 8) What do you think is the optimal scale for a biodiversity tool? * **PA**
 - a. Plot/field level (one field within a farm)
 - b. Farm level (all the land managed within a farm (e.g. also includes small forests patches))
 - c. Landscape level (beyond, large area with all streams, woodlands, cropland, villages ...)
 - d. ...
- 9) What amount of time per year are you willing to invest in biodiversity assessment?
 - a. (hours) : (minutes)
- 10) What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment tool?

The current management of the farm/field.

 - a. Yes/No/Maybe

The amount of trees (and tree species) on the farm/field.

 - b. Yes/No/Maybe

Some easy to record and charismatic species (e.g. birds).

 - c. Yes/No/Maybe
- 11) What should be an input of the biodiversity assessment tool?

*Other ideas? **

The tool-design

- 12) How should the tool be constructed? **PA**
- a. Based only on publicly available maps
 - b. Based on a checklist of the current management and status of the farm/field
 - c. A mixed approach
 - d. ...
- 13) What kind of tool would you like to use? * **PA**
- a. Website on the internet
 - b. Freely available computer program
 - c. QGIS/arcGIS-tool (software to handle maps)
 - d. Excel spreadsheet
 - e. R program (software for data-analysis)
 - f. ...

The validation of the tool

After a theoretical construction of any tool, it is important to validate the outputs with real data. This ensures that the tool really is a good option to be used as proxy. If the validation data shows a different pattern, changes in the tool are desired.

In this section, we would like to ask what species groups you think are relevant or are you interested in to validate the tool?

- 14) What species groups do you think are relevant or interesting to validate the tool? **PA**
- a. Plants
 - b. Birds
 - c. Bats
 - d. Other mammals
 - e. Butterflies
 - f. Pollinators (e.g. bees, bumblebees, ...)
 - g. Spiders
 - h. Other arthropods
 - i. Amphibians & reptiles
 - j. Moths
 - k. Mushrooms
 - l. Soil fauna (e.g. woodlice, millipedes, nematodes, ...)
 - m. Earthworms
 - n. ...

Annex II – Survey respondents characteristics

Figure B1: Respondent characteristics for the questionnaire.

Figure B2: Tool construction preferences according to stakeholders.

Annex III – Meta-analyses

Figure C1: PRISMA-diagram used for the review process.

During the second screening, we related the species groups to the following functional biodiversity groups: autotrophs, pollinators, soil fauna, natural enemies and pest (Table C1) for each effect size. We extracted effect sizes of relevance to this study. As such, we categorized all effect sizes in 71 thematic classes for which the effect size is applicable. Given our focus on agroforestry in agro-environments and landscape contexts, 7 thematic classes were retained. In a following step, we removed effect sizes that were irrelevant due to the reference unit not being an agroecosystem or due to other specifications (Table C2). Tables C3 and C4 provide an overview of the relevant meta-analyses.

Table C1: The effect sizes specifications.

Global	Global topic of the specified effect size
TAG	Class (Table) of the specified effect size
Specification	More specification for TAG
Interaction	Type of interaction affecting the effect size (if relevant), e.g. landscape complexity, age, distance, management, ...
Species group	Species groups for effect sizes were displayed in two ways: (1) simplified, referring to a higher taxon and (2) detailed, referring towards the specified species group (if relevant)
Functional group	Each effect size was assigned to the relevant species group(s): <i>Plants</i> , <i>Pollinators</i> , <i>Soil fauna</i> , <i>Natural enemies</i> and <i>Pest species</i> . Effect sizes referring to bigger species groups, which are not classifiable in functional groups were added to a group assessing biodiversity overall: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall: overall, arthropods, invertebrates, fauna, insects, vertebrates • Plants: plants, trees, understorey, shrubs, bryophytes, lichens, weeds • Pollinators: bees, bumblebees, butterflies, flies, hymenoptera, hoverflies • Soil fauna: spiders, mites, springtails, fungi, microbes, bacteria, worms, millipedes, isopods, beetles, nematodes, detritivores, gastropods, harvestmen, myriapods • Natural enemies: spiders, beetles, birds, herpetofauna, harvestmen, parasitoids, bats • Pest species: bugs, gastropods, grasshoppers, weeds, herbivores
Metric	Abundance (ab), Species richness (SR), Evenness (ev), Simpson-index (Si), Shannon(-Weaver) index (SW), unspecified diversity metric (div), Biomass
Significance	Positive response (+), Not significant (0), Negative response (-)
Effect size	These effect sizes were extracted directly from the articles. If no exact values were mentioned in the article, we used https://plotdigitizer.com/app to extract them.
Reference unit	The unit used as reference

Table C2: Inclusion criteria for separate effect sizes.

<p>Per effect size, the global topic was evaluated. These were grouped into different classes:</p>	<p><i>AES, Abandonment, Afforestation, Agricultural intensification, Agriculture land use, Agroforestry, Bird diversity, Complexity, Composition, Configuration, Connectivity, Conventional farming, Conversion, Crop rotation, Crop diversification, Dead wood, Deforestation, Diversified farming, Ecosystem engineering, Edge effects, Extensive vegetation management vineyards, Fertilization, Field edge, Floral abundance, Floral diversity, Forest edge, Forest grazing, Forest tree diversity, Fragmentation, Grassland, Grassland conversion, Grazing, Grazing exclusion, Habitat age, Habitat diversity, Hedgerows, Heterogeneity, In-field plant diversity, Infrastructure, Insecticides, Integrated farming, Intensive agroecosystem, Invasive species, Land sharing, Land sparing, Low-input agroecosystem, Man-made agroecosystem, Man-made grassland, Management, Mowing, Native crayfish, No fertilization, No tillage, Patch area, Plant diversity, Plantation, Polyculture, Primary, Proximity, Reduced tillage, Restoration, Roads, Scattered trees, Semi-natural habitat, Set-aside land, Short rotation woody crop, silviculture, Small mammals disturbance, Thinning, Urban edge, Urbanization</i></p>
<p>We excluded effect sizes with land use type ‘aquatic’ and then retained:</p>	<p><i>AES, Abandonment, Afforestation, Agroforestry, Complexity, Composition, Configuration, Connectivity, Conventional farming, Conversion, Crop rotation, Crop diversification, Dead wood, Diversified farming, Edge effects, Extensive vegetation management vineyards, Field edge, Floral abundance, Floral diversity, Forest edge, Forest grazing, Forest tree diversity, Fragmentation, Habitat age, Habitat diversity, Hedgerows, Heterogeneity, In-field plant diversity, Integrated farming, Invasive species, Land sharing, Land sparing, Low-input agroecosystem, Man-made agroecosystem, Patch area, Plant diversity, Plantation, Polyculture, Proximity, Restoration, Scattered trees, Semi-natural habitat, Set-aside land, Short rotation woody crop, Urban edge</i></p>
<p>We selected only effect sizes categorized in following classes:</p>	<p><i>Agroforestry, Complexity, Composition, Configuration, Connectivity, Diversified farming, Field edge, Forest grazing, Hedgerows, Heterogeneity, Scattered trees</i></p>
<p>Inclusion of separate effect sizes</p>	<p><i>For the field edge metrics we only used effect sizes concerning woody field edges, stated as ‘arboreal’ or ‘shrub’ as specification. The agroforestry category contained both silvoarable and silvopastoral effect sizes (specified) alongside overall agroforestry. We sorted all effect sizes in our agroforestry section and duplicated the effect sizes specified in silvoarable or silvopastoral systems to use them as well in the specified sections.</i></p>
<p>Refining of the database</p>	<p><i>Agroforestry in agroecosystems was our primary target. We excluded thus ‘diversified farming’ as this practice also includes non-agroforestry practices. We excluded ‘Field edge’ as well as study addressing this topic focused on the effects provoked by implementing flower enhancement. ‘Forest grazing’ was excluded due to its functioning in forest ecosystems. Concerning landscape complexity, we excluded ‘heterogeneity’ as there is both configurational and compositional heterogeneity, which we address separately.</i></p>
<p>Relevance of reference units</p>	<p><i>Our target is to disentangle the effects of integrating agroforestry practices, therefore we excluded effect sizes comparing agroforestry with forests/natural habitat, as agroforestry mostly is a means to convert agroecosystems towards more sustainable systems. For forest grazing, however, forests were kept as comparator as this practice is forest-based.</i></p>

Table C3: The selected meta-analyses, along with its primary conclusion concerning biodiversity, the assessed species groups and regions and the number of effect sizes per study. (black = overall/soil fauna, green = plants, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species). The specified species groups were categorized in the most suitable functionalities. *Only studies used for biodiversity metrics are considered. Letters in parantheses refer to the indexes used in the meta-analysis figures.

Citation	Primary conclusion	Assessed species groups	Region	No. studies	
(Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2011)	Natural enemies have a strong positive response to landscape complexity , pest abundance doesn't show a significant response.	Natural enemies, generalists, specialists Pest species	Global	46	(a)
(Coutinho et al., 2018)	The descriptors of structural complexity at the local scale explained more of the richness and abundance of bees than the descriptors at landscape scale .	Bees (social, solitary, aboveground nesting, belowground nesting)	Global	43	(b)
(Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022)	Increasing landscape complexity through changes in composition, configuration, or heterogeneity significantly and positively affects biodiversity.	Overall, invertebrates Plants, weeds Pollinators Natural enemies, spiders, birds Pest species, weeds	Global	157	(c)
(García de León et al., 2021)	Farmland with hedgerows exhibited higher levels of biodiversity than farmland without and provided similar levels of biodiversity than natural habitat.	Overall, vertebrates, invertebrates Plants	Global	170	(d)
(Marja et al., 2022)	Agri-environment schemes in Europe benefit both abundance and species richness, whereas increasing landscape complexity primarily enhances species richness.	Arthropods	Europe	29	(e)
(Mupepele et al., 2021)	Overall, there was no benefit of agroforestry to biodiversity. silvopastoral showed no difference to forests, pastures or abandoned silvopastures. However, silvoarable systems increased biodiversity compared to cropland by 60%.	Overall, arthropods Birds	Europe	50	(f)
(Prevedello et al., 2018)	Areas with scattered trees support greater levels of biodiversity than open areas and maintain communities that are more similar to habitat patches.	Overall, vertebrates, arthropods Plants, woody plants, herbs	Global	62	(g)
(Shackelford et al., 2013)	Compositional complexity at both landscape and local scales had positive effects on both pollinators and natural enemies, but different effects on different taxa.	Arthropods Pollinators, bees Beetles, parasitoids, spiders Beetles, parasitoids, spiders	Global	46	(h)
(Staton et al., 2019)	Natural enemy abundance increased (+24%), arthropod herbivore/pest abundance decreased (-25%) in silvoarable systems significantly.	Natural enemies Pest species	Temperate regions	19	(i)
(Torralba et al., 2016)	Agroforestry promotes biodiversity, stressing the importance of promoting features and practices that act at a landscape scale.	Overall, arthropods Plants Fungi Birds	Europe	53	(j)

Table C4: Meta-analyses in our database relating agroecological measures with landscape context, along with its primary conclusion concerning biodiversity, the assessed species groups and regions and the number of effect sizes per study. (black = overall/soil fauna, green = plants, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species). The specified species groups were categorized in the most suitable functionalities. *Only studies used for biodiversity metrics are considered. Letters in parantheses refer to the indexes used in the meta-analysis figures. (SR = species richness, ab = abundance).

Citation	Primary conclusion	Assessed species groups	Region	No. studies
(Batáry et al., 2011)	Agri-environmental management enhanced species richness and abundance but its effectiveness towards varies with landscape complexity .	Overall, arthropods Plants Pollinators Birds Herbivores	Europe	47 (SR) 46 (ab) (k)
(Lichtenberg et al., 2017)	Organic farming and higher in-field plant diversity enhanced arthropod abundance, increasing richness as well. Richness on farms embedded in complex relative to simple landscapes	Arthropods Pollinators Detritivores Predators Herbivores	Global	235 (l)
(Scheper et al., 2013)	Pollinator responses to agri-environmental schemes are moderated by landscape context and farmland type, with more positive responses in croplands located in simple (vs. cleared or complex) landscapes.	Pollinators	Europe	57 (SR) 69 (ab) (m)
(Sánchez et al., 2022)	Diversified farming systems have 26% higher species richness than simplified systems, but are highly variable across functional groups and landscape complexity .	Overall Autotrophs Pollinators Decomposers Natural enemies Pests	Global	237 (n)

Table C5: Inclusion criteria for separate effect sizes: interaction effects landscape context and agro-ecological measures.

Selection for interaction effects between agro-ecological measures and landscape context	<p>We filtered the complete dataset for the interaction term: following key words were been used: cleared landscape, simple landscape, complex landscape, distance to semi-natural habitats. We recategorized the latter: cleared = distance +1000m, complex = distance -250m, simple = distance 250-1000m.</p> <p>We excluded average field, number of habitats, percentage arable field and number sown flower species as those effect sizes were not convertible to landscape complexity categorization.</p>
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Annex IV – Tools

We aimed for tools or methods returning a proxy for in situ biodiversity in a terrestrial ecosystem and excluded thus species identification mechanisms (e.g., iNaturalist, ObsIdentify; Annex VII), observation databases (e.g., observation.org; Annex VII) and habitat maps (e.g. Biological valuation map, Habitat mapping layer).

Initially, we used personal knowledge to establish a database, which was extended afterwards with (1) results from following a search using the following terms: “*biodiversity AND ("tool" OR "platform" OR "calculator")*”, inserted in both Google Chrome and Google scholar (December 2022). This resulted in more than 1 million results. We therefore decided to initially evaluate the first 100 results found in Google Scholar and 30 results from Google Chrome, which limited the result to 6 and 5 tools respectively. We decided to use alternative approaches to proceed in the assembling of tools. We extended the database with (2) mentioned/used tools in several papers (Landert et al., 2020; Marshall et al., 2020; Stewart et al., 2022; Tzilivakis et al., 2016), (3) useful tools submitted by project partners and (4) tools suggested in the questionnaire. This resulted in a total number of 55 tools considered in our database (Annex VI).

For each tool, we retrieved the year of last adaptation of the tools and classified their intended application environments (forest, agriculture, urban, aquatic, soil, overall, other). Furthermore, we classified the tools in different interface types via which they can be assessed, such as computer programs specifically designed for the tool (CP), spreadsheets (Excel), geographic information system-tools (QGIS), programming tools (R) and textual/literature guidelines (TG). We then assessed the scale of application. We distinguished three classes within the scale of application: (P) tools that only are applicable on the homogeneous plot- or field level, (L) tools that are applicable on regional or landscape level, but only enable large scale application and (F) tools functioning on farm or landscape level and where users thus can delineate the scale of application to own desire (Figure).

Figure D1: Conceptual figure for the scale of application. Tools functioning on regional scale cannot zoom into the features into a pixel, Tools functioning on plot or field scale cannot zoom out to assess a landscape as such. Tools based on landscape scale are intermediate and can be used to assess more spatial complex units, such as farms.

We further selected tools that might be able to assess biodiversity in agroforestry. Some of the assembled tools mainly provided toolkits or administrative suggestions or were not assessable. These tools were excluded in a first step (Figure D2). Next, we categorized the tools into (1) tools applicable for agroecosystems and (2) tools only applicable for other ecosystems (forest, aquatic, ... only). Hence the need to develop a tool in agroforestry, we excluded tools that did not implement trees, hedgerows or other agroforestry units.

Figure D2: A schematic overview of the purifying of the tools-database.

Figure D3: Underlying variables for the Nonmetric Multidimensional. Contrib = contribution in percentage. (WT = webtool, S = spreadsheet, GIS = geographic information system-tool, R = programming tool, TG = guidelines, CP = computer program, F = farm scale, L = landscape/regional scale, P = plot/field scale, Hedge = hedgerows, AF = agroforestry, SP = Silvopasture, SA = silvoarable, FF = food forest, FG = forest grazing, Woody = implementation of woody features basic characterization, FarmChar = checklist of farm characteristics, Maps = habitat/environment mapping, BioChar = checklist for biotic indicators, LndscpCompl = landscape complexity, MetricBio = one global metric for overall biodiversity, MetricSpGr = one or more metrics for specific species groups, EffAF = effects of different species groups, PropAct = proposed actions towards improving biodiversity, SciTransp = scientific transparency, Free_av = freely availability).

Figure D4: Scree plot for the Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling, with the appropriate stress below 0.2.

Table D1: Reasons to use a value of 0.5.

Driver	Explanation
Plot	<i>If the tool itself is landscape-based, but provides sufficient clarification in its guidelines to make it possible to use it for one plot only, for example when the output values per habitat are given.</i>
Farm	<i>If the tool itself is landscape-based, but provides sufficient clarification in its guidelines to make it possible to use it for a farm and its specific lay-out, for example when the output values per habitat are given.</i>
Free_Av	<i>If the tool itself is not freely available, but the guidelines provide sufficient info to assess a landscape following its protocol.</i>
LndscpCompl	<i>The tool makes use of maps stating the environment of the assessed area, without specifying the implementation of landscape complexity.</i>
MetricBio	<i>The tool returns a proxy for a metric relatable to biodiversity, but does not relate directly to biodiversity (habitat diversity, habitat connectivity)</i>
MetricSpGr	<i>The tool returns a proxy for a metric relatable to a biodiversity group, but does not relate directly to it (pollination)</i>
Questionnaire	<i>If a specific topic was not addresses during the questionnaire, we used an average value.</i>

Figure D5: Principal Component Analysis for biodiversity tool frameworks. StakePOV represents the needs of stakeholders based on the questionnaire.

Figure D6: Underlying variables for the Principal Component Analysis. Contrib = contribution in percentage. (WT = webtool, S = spreadsheet, GIS = geographic information system-tool, R = programming tool, TG = guidelines, CP = computer program, F = farm scale, L = landscape/regional scale, P = plot/field scale, Hedge = hedgerows, AF = agroforestry, SP = Silvopasture, SA = silvoarable, FF = food forest, FG = forest grazing, Woody = implementation of woody features basic characterization, FarmChar = checklist of farm characteristics, Maps = habitat/environment mapping, BioChar = checklist for biotic indicators, LndscpCompl = landscape complexity, MetricBio = one global metric for overall biodiversity, MetricSpGr = one or more metrics for specific species groups, EffAF = effects of different species groups, PropAct = proposed actions towards improving biodiversity, SciTransp = scientific transparency, Free_av = freely availability). Contrib = contribution (%).

Annex V – Meta-analyses

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Annex VI – Biodiversity tools

	1) <i>Authenticity index</i>		
	2) <i>BBI – Belgian Biotic Index</i>		
	3) <i>CPS – Credit Point System</i>		
	5) <i>Biodiversity metric</i>		
	6) <i>MMIF – Multimetric Macroinvertebrate index Flanders</i>		
	?		
	?		
	14) <i>Co\$ting Nature</i>		
	16) <i>Pond biodiversity index</i>		
	17) <i>FRAGSTATS</i>		
	18) <i>Biodiversity Footprint Calculator</i>		
	19) <i>NOP Biodiversity Guidance Compliance Tool</i>		
	20) <i>QBS index</i>		
	21) <i>Greenspace Bird Calculator</i>		

	22) <i>BETs – BEAR Project</i>		?
	23) <i>Ecological Focus Area</i>		?
	24) <i>HFI – Healthy Farm Index</i>		
	25) <i>SPIES</i>		
	26) <i>Guidos Toolbox</i>		?
	27) <i>InFOREST</i>		
	28) <i>Natural Environment Valuation</i>		
	?		
	31) <i>Viridian HydroloGIS</i>		
	32) <i>Berger-Parker index</i>		
	34) <i>FQA - Floristic quality Assessment</i>		
	35) <i>Habitat Hectares</i>		
	38) <i>Fieldprint Calculator</i>		
	39) <i>B-INTACT</i>		?
	41) <i>HSI</i>		
	43) <i>Bee.ok</i>		

	45) Wildlife Woodland Kit		
	46) Agri-environment Biodiversity Index		
	48) Biodiversity Risk filter		
	49) IDA - Index of Agrobiodiversity		
	50) TAPE		
	51) Nature value explorer		
	53) Biodiversiteitsmonitor akkerbouw		
	55) LOOC-B		

Annex VII - Biodiversity databases

Table 6: Different databases that can be used to extract or insert species occurrence data and thus can be used to estimate species richness (and abundance if well-studied area) in areas of interest.

	Full name	Developer/ Partner	Develop- ment*	Location	Link	Reference	
	https://avibase.bsc-eoc.org/avibase.jsp	(Lepage, 2022; Lepage et al., 2014)					
	https://www.gbif.org/en/	(GBIF, 2022)					
	https://nbnatlas.org/	(NBN Trust, 2022)					
	https://www.telmee.nl/?c=portal&m=home	(NDFF, 2023b)					

Developer/supporter: ... = too many to list

*Start date of organization/organized gathering of data, portal sites can be started up later on and observation gathering can exist before this development.

 = linked phone app(s) available

 = Only fauna